

Study of LR models developed for physical traits

Julieta Vera^{1, 2, †}, Cinthia Oyhanarte^{1, 2, †} and María Celeste Peterman^{1, 2, †}

¹Universidad Nacional de José C. Paz, Department of Health and Sports, Leandro N. Alem 4731, B1665KMB José C. Paz, Provincia de Buenos Aires

²Forensic Statistics club

[†]These authors contributed equally to this work

Abstract

Forensic investigations often rely on the use of physical traits to search for the potential person of interest. Physical trait data is collected from victim testimonies, obtained from video-cameras or photos surrounding the crime scene, among others. This data is used to search across databases in order to define potential persons of interest to be further analyzed. Recently, some models have been developed that allow computing likelihood ratios (LR) for physical traits. Rarer characteristics can provide higher LRs in identifications. Here, we exhaustively study the expected LRs considering different characteristics. We aim to provide the forensic practitioners a notion about which values are expected under different scenarios, for example, when the person of interest is the searched one, or if it is not.

Keywords: Likelihood Ratio, Forensic Science, Missing Person, Statistical weight of evidence

Corresponding author: Julieta Vera. E-mail address: julivera0123@gmail.com

1. Introduction

In forensic investigations, a central question often involves determining whether the unidentified person (UP) is the missing person (MP). DNA evidence is crucial in these cases, providing a reliable comparison method through universally accepted scientific techniques [1][2]. Investigations typically consider two hypotheses: H_1 : UP is MP, and H_2 : UP is not MP, with DNA typing playing a key role [3], [4]. Direct DNA samples can be collected from UPs, but for MPs, relatives often provide DNA, necessitating kinship testing [5]. Knowing the familial relationships between the MP and relatives is critical, and multiple family members are often genotyped to create family pedigrees.

The evidence collection process includes both genetic and non-genetic data. Non-genetic evidence, such as testimonies and family interviews, provides crucial details about MP, while information on UP is gathered from remains and surrounding context, including cemetery records [6]. This is particularly important in cases such as child abductions, where the UP may be a living person whose biological identity needs verification [7].

The research of Evett and Weir [1], [8] established the use of Bayes' Theorem to update probabilities based on new evidence. The likelihood ratio (LR) compares the strength of evidence with two competing hypotheses, forming the foundation for the interpretation of complex forensic data [8].

Recent advances in forensic science emphasize genetic databases for identifying missing persons and disaster victims [9], [10]. These methods have become more prominent due to advances in genetic markers and software tools. Although large-scale database searches are essential for open cases, closed cases such as disaster victim identification (DVI) require precise victim counts [11]. Challenges arise when samples are compromised or preliminary data is insufficient, which can reduce statistical power, necessitating further data collection or additional genetic markers [7]. Non-genetic data can improve DNA-based searches, particularly when genetic data alone is insufficient [12].

This study focuses on exhaustively analyzing a mathematical model used to evaluate non-genetic evidence, particularly physical traits [13], [14]. The model accounts for potential errors and introduces a framework to integrate non-genetic data into kinship testing. Using non-genetic data as non-uniform distributions, the model improves the reliability of identification, particularly in challenging cases. The methods are available through the open-source R package `mispitools` [15], aiding forensic practitioners in applying these techniques effectively.

2. Methods

The objective of this study was to evaluate how varying non-genetic characteristics and their corresponding likelihoods under two hypotheses, H_1 (the unidentified person, UP, is the missing person, MP) and H_2 (the UP is not the MP), impact the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence. Instead of focusing on genetic data, we simulated a range of nongenetic traits and calculated the likelihood ratio (LR) to assess how these traits influence the expected KL divergence in both directions. This approach provides insight into how well non-genetic evidence can distinguish between H_1 and H_2 .

Using the `mispitools` package [15], we simulated 10,000 cases where UP and MP were characterized by non-genetic traits such as biological sex (S), hair color (C) and age (A). These traits were treated as follows: hair color was modeled as a categorical variable with five possible values (1 = brown, 2 = black, 3 = blond, 4 = auburn, 5 = red), biological sex was dichotomous (F = female, M = male) and age was treated as a continuous variable ranging from 0 to 100 years. For each simulation, the likelihood of observing these characteristics under both hypotheses was calculated.

Under H_1 , the likelihood P represents the probability of observing the characteristics of the UP assuming that the UP is indeed the MP, based on prior data such as testimony, legal documents, or direct observation. Under H_2 , the likelihood Q reflects the probability of observing these characteristics assuming that the UP is not related to the MP and is drawn randomly from a reference population. For Q , we incorporated simulated population frequencies for each non-genetic trait (e.g., population distributions for hair color, sex ratios, and age demographics) to account for how common or rare the observed traits are in the general population. Simulations are provided by `mispitools`.

We then calculated the LR for each scenario, comparing the likelihood of the characteristics under H_1 and H_2 . From these LRs, we calculated two key metrics: forward KL divergence

$$KL = E [\log_{10}(LR)] | P$$

which measures the expected information gain assuming that H_1 is true, and reverse KL divergence

$$\overline{KL} = E [\log_{10}(LR)] | Q$$

which assesses the expected information gain assuming that H_2 is true. These divergences help quantify the amount of evidence non-genetic characteristics contribute to distinguishing between H_1 and H_2 .

The inclusion of a minimum probability value ($1e-12$) was necessary to handle cases where the characteristics observed in H_1 could

have a near zero probability in H2 (e.g., rare combinations of age, sex, and hair color). This adjustment ensures that the KL divergence remains finite, even in cases of extreme exclusion, where certain traits may be highly unlikely in the general population but still possible under H1.

By linking LR calculations to the KL divergence framework [16], this methodology provides a clearer understanding of the information value of non-genetic characteristics in cases of missing person identification. The KL divergence metrics offer a robust method to evaluate how well the non-genetic evidence distinguishes between the two hypotheses. All simulations were conducted using mispitoools, allowing efficient computation of LR and KL divergences across a wide range of scenarios. This approach offers a valuable tool for forensic experts in assessing the strength of non-genetic evidence in complex identification cases.

3. Results

The results of this study demonstrate how various nongenetic characteristics and population frequencies influence the KL divergence, which quantifies the ability to distinguish between two hypotheses: H1 (the unidentified person, UP, is the missing person, MP) and H2 (the UP is not the MP). By simulating cases with varying hair color, biological sex, and age, we observed the effect of these traits on the likelihood ratio LR and the corresponding KL divergence in both directions: $KL(P||Q)$, representing the information gain under H1 and $KL(Q||P)$, representing the information gain under H2.

Figure 1 explores the effect of the missing person age range (MP_r) on the KL divergence. As shown in the left panel, the forward KL divergence $KL(P||Q)$ decreases as MP_r increases, indicating that as the possible age range for MP widens, the ability to discriminate between H1 and H2 weakens. Similarly, the right panel shows that the reverse KL divergence $KL(Q||P)$ also decreases with increasing age range, highlighting that a broader age range reduces the information gained against H2. This suggests that narrowing the possible age range of the MP can significantly improve the discriminatory power of the non-genetic evidence.

Figure 1. Impact of varying the missing person age range (MP_r) on the KL divergence. The left panel shows the forward KL divergence, representing the expected information gain when H1 is true, as a function of the missing person age range. As the age range increases, the divergence decreases, indicating reduced discriminatory power. The right panel shows the reverse KL divergence, which measures the expected information gain when H2 is true. Here, a similar trend is observed, where increasing the age range lowers the KL divergence, reflecting decreased evidence against H2 as the possible match becomes less specific.

Figure 2 examines the impact of the frequency of the female population $P(F)$ on the KL divergence. In the left panel, the KL divergence decreases as the proportion of females in the population increases. This indicates that when the observed traits (e.g., biological sex of women) are more common, the evidence to support H1 becomes weaker. The right panel shows a similar trend for the reverse KL divergence, where a higher frequency of females in the population reduces the strength of evidence against H2. These findings emphasize that the traits more prevalent in the population contribute less to the LR, decreasing its value in identification scenarios.

Figure 2. Impact of the population frequency of females $P(F)$ on the KL divergence. The left panel shows the forward KL divergence, which measures the expected information gain when H1 is true, as a function of the population frequency of females. As the frequency increases, the divergence decreases, showing that when females are more common in the population, the evidence for H1 weakens. The right panel displays the reverse KL divergence, which measures the expected information gain when H2 is true. A similar decline is observed as the population frequency of females increases, indicating that a higher proportion of females in the population reduces the ability to exclude H2.

Figure 3 focuses on the impact of missing person's hair color (MP_c) on KL divergence. The left panel shows that KL increases as hair color becomes less common, with rarer traits such as auburn or red hair providing stronger evidence for H1. The right panel illustrates a similar pattern for \overline{KL} , where rare hair colors offer more information against H2. This highlights the significant role that unique or less common traits play in enhancing the likelihood ratio, making them particularly valuable in identification cases where such traits are available.

Figure 3. Impact of the missing person's hair color (MP_c) on the KL divergence. The left panel shows KL, representing the expected information gain when H1 is true, across different hair color categories (1 = brown, 2 = black, 3 = blond, 4 = auburn, 5 = red). The KL divergence increases as hair color becomes less common, indicating that rarer hair colors provide stronger evidence for H1. The right panel presents the reverse KL divergence, which also increases for less common hair colors, showing that rare hair colors provide stronger evidence to exclude H2. These results highlight the importance of unique phenotypic traits in contributing to the strength of the likelihood ratio.

4. Conclusions

This study highlights the impact of nongenetic characteristics, such as biological sex, age, and hair color, on the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence in forensic identification scenarios. The results show that rarer traits, particularly in hair color, contribute more significantly to distinguishing between H1 (the UP is the MP) and H2 (the UP is not the MP). As traits become more common in the general population, their contribution to the likelihood ratio weakens, reducing the discriminatory power of evidence.

Furthermore, narrowing the possible age range or focusing on unique traits improves the information gain, as reflected in higher KL divergences. These findings suggest that nongenetic traits, when properly utilized, can enhance the strength of forensic identification, particularly in cases where genetic data may be limited or unavailable.

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